

Autopilot Design for a Generic based Expendable Launch Vehicle Using Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) Control Approach

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Abstract

This paper explores the application of Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control synthesis for an autopilot of a generic based Expendable Launch Vehicle (ELV) during ascent flight, in pitch plane. Thus, gives some introduction about the fundamental aspects of the LQG control theory and it shows an application option through an example how the value of the initial covariance matrix of estimation error, was effectively used to meet design objective of a reduced *percentage overshoot* and *settling time*. The movement of an Expendable Launch Vehicle (ELV) can be modeled with a linear time invariant dynamic system, which must be controlled by a flight controller especially during the boost phase. The synthesis and analysis of the stability and other qualitative control parameters were done using Matlab/Simulink.

Keywords: LQG control, Expendable Launch Vehicle, Autopilot, Matlab/Simulink

1. Introduction

An autopilot is a closed-loop system inside a Guidance Navigation and Control System (GNC). The primary role of an autopilot is to stabilize the vehicle and to control the attitude angle. It is also of

prime importance to minimize the deviation from nominal trajectory and to limit the induced angle-of-attack in response to wind. The vehicle flight control system will be required to meet two conflicting requirements: to minimize trajectory deviations since excessive guidance correction results in payload penalty, and to minimize the angle-of-attack excursion in order to reduce the resulting bending moment or in other words, ensure structural integrity of the vehicle. Depending on which requirement the emphasis is made on, the control structure will be different. The final decision must be made by considering the specific mission (what is the worst tolerable deviation from the nominal trajectory at the end of the flight?) and the structural configuration of the airframe (what is the maximum lateral force that it can withstand?). Solving such trade-off problem of course is out of the scope of this work. Rather the emphasis has been put on the problem of minimizing the deviation from nominal trajectory of the ELV as it travels up to an altitude of about 100Km above the earth surface [5].

An Expendable Launch Vehicle (ELV) is used to carry a payload into space. The vehicles are designed to be used only once (i.e. they are "expended" during a single flight), and their components are not recovered after launch. The vehicle typically consists of several rocket stages, discarded one by one as the vehicle gains altitude and speed. The ELV design differs from that of reusable launch systems, where the vehicle is launched and recovered more than once. Reuse might seem to make systems like the Space Shuttle more cost effective than ELVs, but in practice launches using ELVs have been less expensive than Shuttle launches. Most satellites are currently launched using expendable launchers; they are perceived as having a low risk of mission failure, a short time to launch and a relatively low cost. A Shuttle orbiter is a major national asset, and its high cost (far more than a single expendable launch vehicle) and presence of a crew require stringent "man rated" flight safety precautions that increase launch and payload costs. Only five orbiters were built, and the unexpected loss of two (Challenger and Columbia) significantly impacted the capacity and viability of the Shuttle program. Each loss also resulted in an extended hiatus in Shuttle flights compared to that following most expendable launch failure, each of which impacted only that model of launcher. For these reasons it is generally agreed that the Space Shuttle has not delivered on its original promise to reduce the costs of constructing and launching payloads into orbit. The Shuttle was originally intended to replace expendable launchers in the launching of satellites, but after the loss of Challenger the Shuttle was reserved for previously planned missions and those requiring a crew [6].

In this work we consider the atmospheric ascent flight and the design selection point are traditionally were the load created by the non-zero angle-of-attack is the most extreme. The size of the load with the most difficult design points during a boost phase trajectory is the transonic region and maximum pressure regions. The transonic region is characterized by large fluctuations in the aerodynamic derivative coefficients. The dramatic changes create elevated levels of uncertainty in the linearized equations, and emphasize the importance of quality controller during this region. The maximum dynamic pressure on the vehicle also places increased importance on controller quality.

During this section of the trajectory, the structural is characterized by dynamic pressure and angle-of-attack ($Q\alpha$), serves as a physical limitation that must be accommodated by the control law. These historic points; Mach 1.0, occurs 72 seconds into the boost phase and the time at which maximum dynamic pressure, Q , occurs is at exactly 82 seconds. For the ELV, these two points occur within seconds of each other, approximately 72 seconds after launch [4]. Therefore, only one point (Mach 1.0 and $Q = 480psf$) during the mission trajectory is used.

In this paper we shall give a short view of the so-called Linear Quadratic Gaussian theory, which can be consulted for more details in [1], [2] and [3]. This article discusses an example of a Pitch-Plane autopilot design for a generic based Expendable Launch Vehicle (ELV) for a typical wind gust rejection scheme. In order to realize the LQG autopilot we employed the separation principle, which means that we were able to design the LQG controller in two steps. First, the design of the LQR

(Linear Quadratic Regulator), and then we have to find a state estimator, an LQE (Linear Quadratic Estimator) applying a modified cost function.

2. Mathematical Description of an ELV

In this section, the mathematical description for ELV in pitch plane is presented; including the aspects of state-space representation. The equations of motion of an ELV are complicated by the fact that the vehicle has time-varying mass and inertia. There can also be relative motion between various masses within the vehicle and origin of the body axes, such as fuel sloshing, engine gimbal rotation, and vehicle flexibility. Expendable Launch vehicle dynamics are generally described by ‘short-period’ equations of motion during the atmospheric flight. Although, the ‘short-period’ equations are the results of a linearization process, the lateral dynamics on the pitch and yaw axes can be coupled by the vehicle roll rate. In fact, when the launch vehicle has a negligible roll rate, an action on the pitch plane produces an effect in the yaw plane.

There are many possible frames of reference to present the forces and moments that influence the motion of the vehicle in its pitch plane. The three set of axes used in this study are shown in Figure 1. The earth-fixed coordinate frame $(X_E - Z_E)$, which coincide with the trajectory plane with $X_E -$ axis and $Z_E -$ axis coincide with the local horizontal and vertical lines of the earth at the launch pad. The non-rotational vehicle reference system (X_b, Z_b) , where $X_b -$ axis lies along the longitudinal axis of the vehicle, positive in the nominal direction of positive thrust acceleration. The $Z_b -$ axis completes for a standard right-handed system. The trajectory inertial system (X_I, Z_I) that is tangent to the nominal trajectory of the vehicle. It is obtained from the earth-fixed coordinate frame by rotation of θ_0 (nominal attitude) about the $Z_E \times X_E -$ axis. Neglecting the effects of bending and sloshing and lags due to actuator and instrumentation, the linearized equation of motion of the vehicle have been derived in details in [7] and take the form:

Force equation:

$$\ddot{z} = -\left[\frac{T_T - D}{M} + g \cos(\theta_0)\right]\theta - \frac{L_\alpha \alpha}{M} + \frac{T_C \delta}{M} = -\frac{(T_T - D)\theta}{M} - \frac{L_\alpha \alpha}{M} + \frac{T_C \delta}{M} \quad (1)$$

Moment equation:

$$\ddot{\theta} = \mu_\alpha \alpha + \mu_c \delta, \quad (2)$$

Angle-of-attack:

$$\alpha = \theta + \frac{\dot{z}}{v} + \alpha_w, \quad (3)$$

where, gust angle of attack, Thrust Vector deflection angle, and Control moment coefficient are given as follows respectively:

$$\alpha_w = \left\{ -\left(\frac{v_w}{v} \right) \right\}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mu_\alpha = \left(\frac{L_\alpha l_\alpha}{I} \right), \quad (5)$$

$$\mu_c = \frac{T_C l_C}{I}. \quad (6)$$

where $D -$ drag; $I -$ moment of inertia of the vehicle about the pitch axis; $l_c -$ distance from mass centre of the vehicle to engine swivel point; $l_\alpha -$ distance from mass centre of vehicle to centre of

pressure; L_α – aerodynamic load per unit angle of attack; M – mass of vehicle; T_c – control thrust; v – forward velocity of the vehicle; v_w – wind velocity; Z – normal displacement of the vehicle relative to inertial frame; α – angle- of-attack; θ – perturbation attitude error; θ_0 – nominal attitude angle relative to the earth-fixed reference; $\dot{\theta}$ – attitude rate; $\ddot{\theta}$ – attitude acceleration. The launch azimuth is assumed to be directly east.

The derivations and models assumption that lead to the linearized equations of motion for the LV stated in this section follow those stated by Greensite A. L.

Figure 1: Launcher Model in the pitch plane

2.1. State Space Model of the hypothetical ELV

For a linear time invariant system described by the equation below,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= Ax + Bu \\ y &= Cx + Du \quad x(0) = x_0, \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

The pitch- plane model for the ELV, considering actuator deflection as the only input to the plant is given as [9],

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \\ \ddot{\theta} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \mu_\alpha & 0 & \mu_\alpha \\ -L_\alpha/Mv & 0 & -L_\alpha/Mv \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z}/v \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ \mu_c & \mu_\alpha \\ T_c/Mv & -L_\alpha/Mv \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \delta \\ \alpha_w \end{bmatrix} \\ \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z}/v \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

The actuator deflection δ is a known input to the plant, whereas the wind-induced angle- of-attack α_w is an unknown input. This has to be estimated and thus, it becomes an input estimate problem, unfortunately outside the scope of this research. The attitude angle (θ) and body rate ($\dot{\theta}$) are available on-line during flight. The lateral drift (\dot{z}) is estimated and used thereby improving the cost

and weight significantly, since there is no need for a separate sensor to measure the lateral drift. The estimated lateral drift is used to limit the vehicle angle-of-attack in high dynamic pressure region (Q) regions of the ascent. Vehicle lateral loads are proportional to the product of Q and total angle-of-attack.

The following sets of parameters in Table 1 are for a generic launch vehicle based on the work of Ramnath [8]. These parameters were evaluated for a time, $t = 72\text{sec}$ in-flight. It should be noted here that the values for aerodynamic moment coefficient, control moment coefficient and forward velocity presented in Table 1, was from (Amol A..).

Table 1: Numeric Parameters for a generic ELV evaluated at $t = 72\text{sec}$.

S/N	Parameter	Expressional value	Numeric value
1.	$q(t)$	$t^2 \exp(-1.72+0.00975\times t - 0.000276\times t^2)$	0.23atm
2.	D	$684\times q, \text{Ibs}$	$1.363\times 10^6 \text{ N}$
3.	T_c	592000 Ibs	$2.634\times 10^6 \text{ N}$
4.	$M(t)$	$171200 - 815\times t, \text{slugs}$	$1.642\times 10^6 \text{ Kg}$
5.	T_T	$(893 - 1.43\times t)\times 10^4 \text{ Ibs}$	$3.516\times 10^7 \text{ N}$
6.	μ_c	-	3.4858m/s^2
7.	μ_α	-	14.7805deg/s^2
8.	v	$\mu_\alpha / v = 0.01958$	754.877 m / s
9.	v_w	-	20 m / s

This is due to the fact that Ramnath considered a Space Shuttle in his work and ours here is an ELV with a different distance from mass center to engine swivel point, l_c , and center of pressure, l_α . The forward velocity as given in Table 1 was inferred from the *state space* description of the ELV in (8).

The State-space model of a typical highly aerodynamically unstable Launcher in the highly dynamic pressure region is given in [10] as,

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 14.7805 & 0 & 0.01958 \\ -100.858 & 1 & -0.1256 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 3.4858 \\ 20.42 \end{bmatrix} \delta + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 14.7805 \\ -94.8557 \end{bmatrix} \alpha_w, y = [1 \ 0 \ 0] \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{9}$$

3. System Analysis (Continuous Time)

In this section, the model as described in (9) is subjected to a Dirac’s impulse investigation to unveil its behavior. Also, Controllability and Observability of the system will be determined to ensure the applicability of the LQG approach.

It is expected to analyze the pure dynamics by studying the transient response of the hypothetical ELV to the Dirac’s delta or impulse function as a test input. It is given as an impulse with rectangular shape with width t_1 and its area equals one.

$$\delta(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{pro.....}t \geq t_1 \\ \frac{1}{t_1}, & \text{pro....}0 \leq t < t_1 \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

In Simulink we used two blocks for step function *Step* as shown in Fig 4. The impulse starts in time 1 second and ending in time 3 seconds with amplitude 0.5, this satisfy's the definition of Dirac's impulse function. Its area is $0.5(3-1) = 1$. [11].

Figure 2: Simulink model for Dirac's impulse investigation

Thus, the response of the ELV as defined by (10) to Dirac's impulse (with zero initial conditions) is depicted in Fig. 3. The increasing nature of the pitch angle as time increases is due to the fact that the system is unstable. This is also evident from the open-loop eigenvalues of the system; $S_{1,2,3} = -3.9143, 3.7807, 0.0080$.

Figure 3: Impulse response of the open-loop ELV

3.1. Controllability and Observability

A system is said to be controllable if a control vector $u(t)$ exist that will transfer the system from any initial state $x(t_0)$ to some final state $x(t)$ in a finite time interval. Consider a system described as in equation (5), sufficient condition for complete state controllability is that the $n \times n$ matrix

$$M = [B : AB : \dots : A^{n-1}B], \quad (11)$$

Contains n linearly independent row or column vectors, i.e. is of the rank n (that is, the matrix is non-singular, i.e. the determinant is non-zero). Equation (12) is called the controllability matrix.

The system described by equation (5) is completely observable if the $n \times n$ matrix

$$N = [C^T : A^T C^T : \dots : (A^T)^{n-1} C^T], \quad (12)$$

Is of the rank n , i.e. is non-singular having a non-zero determinant. Equation (12) is called the Observability matrix [12].

For the hypothetical ELV described by equation (10), the system was found to be completely controllable and observable, hence makes the system suitable for LQG controller design.

4. The LQG Controller Design

In this section, the adopted control strategy is discussed, and fully simulated in Simulink with the goal of obtaining the following time-domain characteristics of; *rise time* less than 1 second, *settling time* of less than 3 seconds, *percentage overshoot* less than 10%, and with a steady state error of less than 2%, for controlling the pitch angle of 0.05 radian (3 degrees).

Linear Quadratic Gaussian (LQG) control consists of a technique for designing optimal dynamic regulators, based on the state-space system modeling. Technically, it comprises of a *Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR)* and a *Kalman Filter* based observer. Fig. 4 depicts the schematic block diagram of LQG control

Figure 4: Schematic block for LQG controlled plant

This technique is based on the search of the tradeoff between regulation performance and control efforts, and it takes into account process disturbances and measurement noises. Basically, the LQG approach addresses the problem where we consider a system dynamic model perturbed by a dynamical noise w , and a state observation corrupted by measurement noise v affecting the sensors data acquisition. The LQG regulator comprises an optimal state-feedback gain and a *Kalman filter* state estimator. This technique requires a linearized state-space model of the system with the addition of the noise effect.

4.1. The Optimal Regulator

The LQG design consists of obtaining the feedback control law in the form $u = -K\hat{x}$ which optimizes the regulation index given by a quadratic performance criterion:

$$J = \int_0^{\infty} (x^T Q x + u^T R u) dt, \quad (13)$$

where Q , and R are weighting matrices that define the tradeoff between regulation performance and control efforts, i.e. the relative weight of how fast the state $x(t)$ goes to zero and the magnitude of the control efforts u . A first selection for the matrices Q and R is given by *Bryson's rule*: select Q and R diagonal with

$$Q_{ii} = \frac{1}{\max \dots \text{acceptable} \dots \text{value} \dots \text{of} \dots x_i^2} \dots \dots \dots i \in \{1, 2, \dots, l\}$$

$$R_{jj} = \frac{1}{\max \dots \text{acceptable} \dots \text{value} \dots \text{of} \dots u_j^2} \dots \dots \dots j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$$
(14)

where Q is an $l \times l$ symmetric positive-definite matrix, and R an $m \times m$ symmetric positive-definite matrix. In essence the Bryson's rule scales the variables that appear in equation (13) so that the *maximum acceptable value for each term is one*. This is especially important when the unit used for the different components of u and x makes the values for these variables numerically different from each other.

Although Bryson's rule sometimes gives good results, often it is just the starting point to a trail-and-error iterative design procedure aimed at obtaining desirable properties for the closed-loop system [13]. For this research, the following values of weighing coefficient were selected in accordance with Bryson's rule;

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} 2.5 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 173.6 \end{bmatrix}, R = 0.1$$
(15)

For a time invariant system, the LQR gain matrix K is obtained by solving the algebraic Riccati equation as given in (17) and taking

$$K = R^{-1} B^T P$$
(16)

$$PA + A^T P + Q - PBR^{-1} B^T P = 0,$$
(17)

The Matlab function $[K, P, E] = lqr(A, B, Q, R)$ was use to solve (17) and the coefficients associated with the Riccati equation were obtained as P , hence the appropriate LQR gain matrix K , for the situation at hand was obtained and the corresponding closed-loop eigenvalues E , for the system as;

$$K = [2700.2 \quad 471.2 \quad -38.2],$$
(18)

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 65684 & 11435 & -1939 \\ 11435 & 1991 & -338 \\ -1939 & -338 & 57 \end{bmatrix},$$
(19)

$$E = \begin{bmatrix} -851.0715 \\ -5.6098 \\ -5.7021 \end{bmatrix}.$$
(20)

4.2. Kalman Filter

Kalman filter is an optimal recursive filter that estimates the state of dynamic system from noisy measurements. It was introduced in the beginning of 1960s and since then many different variant of the Kalman filter has been developed. Kalman filter analyses a dynamic systems' behavior with external and measurement noise. We suppose an external stochastic turbulent air and internal noise at the same time. Thus, there exist, in our case, two types of noises (external, internal). We will calculate with an external stochastic noise (for example the wind turbulence), and an internal random measurement

noise. The two random noises (external disturbance and sensor) are white, Gaussian (normal) zero-mean stationary vector processes. We know the covariance matrices, and the external disturbance noise has a disturbance input matrix G . To find a controller which stabilizes our plant, we have to solve a stochastic integral problem [14]. In general the output y is affected by measurement noise and the process dynamics are also affected by disturbance, specifically turbulence of atmosphere. In light of this, a more reasonable model for the process is presented in (21) instead of (7).

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= Ax + Bu + Gw, \\ y &= Cx + v. \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

where w and v are zero-mean Gaussian noise processes (uncorrelated from each other) with power spectrum,

$$S_w(w) = 0.0326 \quad S_v(\omega) = 0.002, \tag{22}$$

Thus, the process and measurement covariance matrices are defined as $Q_N = Ew_t w_t^T$, and $R_N = Ev_t v_t^T$. and were adopted to have typical values as shown in (23).

$$Q_N = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.2317 & -1.4873 \\ 0 & -1.4873 & 9.5450 \end{bmatrix}, \quad R_N = \begin{bmatrix} 0.002 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.002 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.002 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{23}$$

The covariance matrix of the estimation error satisfies the Riccati equation given in (24) and the initial value for the covariance matrix of estimation error was taken as in (25)

$$\begin{aligned} AP + PA' + BQB' - PC'R^{-1}CP &= \dot{P}, \\ P(t_0) &= P_0. \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

$$P_0 = \text{diag}([S_w S_v \quad S_w S_v \quad S_w S_v]) = \text{diag}([6.52 \times 10^{-5} \quad 6.52 \times 10^{-5} \quad 6.52 \times 10^{-5}]) \tag{25}$$

The Kalman gain L is as given in (26). Kalman filter as an observer was used in this research to obtain the estimate of the state variable, i.e. \hat{x} . The filter equation in (27) was fully implemented in Simulink, depicted in Figure. 5.

$$L = PC'R_N^{-1}. \tag{26}$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = A\hat{x} + Bu + L(y - \hat{y}), \tag{27}$$

$$\hat{y} = C\hat{x}.$$

Figure 5: Simulink model of the implemented Kalman

Typically the Kalman filter is executed in two repeating steps. The prediction is the first step of the Kalman filter. The predicted state, or better the a priori state is calculated by neglecting the dynamic noise and solving the differential equations that describe the *dynamic model*. Thus, for any $t \geq s$ the optimal estimates $x_{t|s}$ satisfy the recursion

$$x_{t+1|s} = A_t x_{t|s}, \quad t \geq s. \tag{28}$$

The error covariance matrix satisfy the equation

$$P_{t+1|s} = A_t P_{t|s} A_t^T + Q_{t+1}, \quad t \geq s. \tag{29}$$

In the second step the state is corrected with the *observation model*, so that the error covariance of the estimation is minimized. In this sense it is an optimal estimator. This procedure is repeated for each time step with the state of the previous time step as initial value. Therefore Kalman filter is called a recursive filter. In mathematical terms, the optimal estimate $x_{t|t}$ is calculated by the optimal prediction $x_{t|t-1}$ and a new measurement y_t by the equation

$$x_{t|t} = x_{t|t-1} + L(y_t - C_t x_{t|t-1}), \tag{30}$$

where the matrix L determined together with the error covariance matrix P from (26) and (24) respectively.

Hence, for the specific choice of Q_N and R_N as presented in (23) and P_0 as given in (25), the Kalman filter as an estimator was fully simulated in Simulink as shown in Figure 6, with initial state as $\hat{x} = [0 \ 0 \ 0]^T$ was used to obtain the following results,

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} 0.9721 & 1.2165 & 0 \\ 1.2165 & 59.8096 & 0 \\ -12.0148 & -383.8899 & 0 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{31}$$

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.001944 & 0.002433 & -0.02403 \\ 0.002433 & 0.1196 & -0.7678 \\ -0.02403 & -0.7678 & 5.052 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{32}$$

$$eig(A - LC) = eig \left(\begin{bmatrix} -0.9721 & -0.2165 & 0 \\ 13.564 & -59.8096 & 0.0196 \\ -88.8432 & 384.8899 & -0.1256 \end{bmatrix} \right) = \begin{bmatrix} -59.8858 \\ -1.0221 \\ 0.0005 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{33}$$

5. Numerical simulation of Autopilot and Results

In this section, a plant-observer [15] arrangement was used to synthesize the LQG autopilot in Simulink as shown in Figure 6, with the reference set point and initial conditions for the state vector as given below; respectively.

$$r = [0.05 \ 0 \ 0]^T. \tag{34}$$

$$x_0 = [0.012 \ 0 \ 0]^T. \tag{35}$$

The autopilot based on the proposed control scheme, was simulated using P_0 as tuning parameter. Although several simulations over a wide range of values were performed, just two cases are shown. Figure 7 shows the result of the simulation for P_0 as given in (25).

In practice this lead to large matrices L and fast poles of the observer’s closed-loop matrices. When R_N is very large, the measurement noise is large so the optimal estimator is much conservative in reacting to deviations of \hat{y} from y . This generally leads to smaller matrices and slow poles of the observer’s close-loop matrices. For the choice of P_0 as given in (36), a re-simulation of the LQG autopilot in Figure. 6 gave the result in Figure. 8.

$$P_0 = \text{diag}([6.52 \times 10^{-3} \quad 6.52 \times 10^{-3} \quad 6.52 \times 10^{-3}]) \tag{36}$$

Figure 8: Set-point command tracking of LQG autopilot with increased P_0

The first question to ask about an LQG controller is whether or not the closed-loop system will be stable. To answer this question we collect all the equations that define the closed-loop system:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu, \quad y = Cx, \tag{37}$$

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = (A - LC)\hat{x} + Bu + Ly, \quad u = -K\hat{x}. \tag{38}$$

To check the stability of this system it is more convenient to consider the dynamics of the estimation error $e = x - \hat{x}$ instead of the state estimate \hat{x} . To this effect we replace in (37) and (38) \hat{x} by $x - e$, which yields:

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu = (A - BK)x + BKe, \quad y = Cx, \tag{39}$$

$$\dot{e} = (A - LC)e, \quad u = -K(x - e). \tag{40}$$

This can be written in matrix notation as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{e} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A - BK & BK \\ 0 & A - LC \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ e \end{bmatrix}, \quad y = \begin{bmatrix} C & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ e \end{bmatrix}. \tag{41}$$

Thus, for this work, (41) can be expressed as in (42). *Separation Principle*: the eigenvalues of the closed-loop system (41) are given by those of the state-feedback regulator dynamics $A - BK$ together with those of the state-estimator dynamics $A - LC$. Thus, (43) justifies the Separation Principle. In case these both matrices are asymptotically stable, then so is the closed-loop in (41), [16]. But from the six eigenvalues in (43) it could be clearly seen that the last eigenvalue is positive, this is not a problem because the last three eigenvalues are for the state-estimator dynamics $A - LC$, and it being stable or unstable- its status does not make the closed-loop system unstable. Most important is the closed-loop of the process $A - BK$ and the effect of the state-estimator on it. The simulated results in Fig. 12 and 13 and (43) prove the fact of this claim; the designed state-estimator does asymptotically stabilize the closed-loop process.

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{\theta} \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \ddot{z} \\ \dot{\hat{\theta}} \\ \ddot{\theta} \\ \ddot{z} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -9398 & -1642 & 133 & 9413 & 1642 & -133 \\ -55240 & -9620 & 780 & 55139 & 9621 & -780 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -0.9721 & -0.2165 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 13.5640 & -59.8096 & 0.0196 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -88.8432 & 384.8899 & -0.1256 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z} \\ \hat{\theta} \\ \dot{\hat{\theta}} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix},$$

$$y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta \\ \dot{\theta} \\ \dot{z} \\ \hat{\theta} \\ \dot{\hat{\theta}} \\ \dot{z} \end{bmatrix}. \tag{42}$$

The eigenvalues associated with (43) are

$$eig(A) = \begin{bmatrix} -852.52 \\ -6.5041 \\ -2.9721 \\ -59.89 \\ -1.0221 \\ 0.0006 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{43}$$

6. Conclusion and Discussion of Results

The obtained numerical simulations results lead to the conclusion that the control strategy based on the LQG theory stabilizes the system exponentially and the synthesized autopilot has an asymptotic stability. The former is deduced from simulated response of the pitch angle and pitch angle rate while the later is based on the result of the closed-loop eigenvalues of the system.

Also, it was proved here that the value of the initial covariance matrix of estimation error, P_0 , could be used effectively to attain design goal of a reduced *percentage overshoot* and *settling time* as could be seen from the results in Figure 8. Also, the autopilot meets all the design goals as well as effectively minimizing error (comparing P_0 and P in (36) and (32) respectively).

LQG has been demonstrated for the critical time instant (high dynamic pressure region) of the flight duration for a generic based ELV. This is an interesting result for the reason that the problem of ELV attitude stabilization constitutes a highly nonlinear control system problem and the application of linear approaches represents an attractive issue in terms of real-time implementation.

In LQG design, the required states are estimated eliminating the need for additional sensors but at the cost of time and the number calculations involved.

References

- [1] Roland S. Burns, 2001. "Advanced Control Engineering", Professor of Control Engineering Department of Mechanical & Marine Engineering University of Plymouth, UK.
- [2] Albertos P. and A. Sala, 2004. "Multivariable Control Systems", An Engineering Approach.
- [3] João Pedro Hespanha, 2007. "LQG/LQR Controller Design", University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB).
- [4] Philippe Le Fur, 1989. "An asymptotic approach in the preliminary design of Launch vehicle control system", Masters of Science Thesis, Department Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT).
- [5] Lt. Hague Tyler Nicklause, 2000 "An application of H_2/H_∞ Robust Control Synthesis to Launch Vehicle ascent", Masters of Science Thesis, Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT).
- [6] http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Expendable_launch_system.
- [7] Greensite A.L, 1970. "Analysis and design of Space Vehicle Flight Control Systems", Volume II Spartan Books, New York.
- [8] Ramnath, R.V, 1973. "A New Approach in the Design of Time Varying Control System with application to space shuttle Boost", Proc. IFAC congress, Geneva, Italy.
- [9] Sreeja S, Dr. A Dinesh Pai, V. R Lalithambika, K Sivan, 2004. "Launch Vehicle Trajectory Reconstruction Considering Wind Estimation from Flight Data Using Kalman Filter".
- [10] Amol A. Khalate, Abdul Naseer, Sheelu Jose and M. V. Dhekane, 2007. "Multi-Objective Control of Aerodynamically Unstable Launcher", Proceedings of the 15th Mediterranean Conference on Control & Automation, Athens-Greece.
- [11] Steven T. Karris, 2006. "Introduction to Simulink with Engineering Applications", Orchard Publications.
- [12] Robert L. Williams II, Douglas A. Lawrence, 2007. "Linear State-space Control Systems".
- [13] Gene F. Franklin, J. David Powell, Abbas Emami- Naeni, 2006. "Feedback Control of Dynamic Systems", Fifth Edition, NJ, Prentice.
- [14] Mohinder S. Grewal, Angus P. Andrews, 2001. "Kalman Filtering: Theory and Practise Using MATLAB", Second Edition. A Wiley- Interscience Publication.
- [15] Balázs Kulcsár, 2000. "LQG/LTR Controller design for an Aircraft model", Department of Control and Transport Automation Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary.
- [16] P. Albertos, A.Sala, 2004. "Multivariable Control systems: An Engineering Approach", Springer.